

Supplemental Table S2. Current (as of 2022) research articles with nose flaps utilized in their method section. Included are the journal publication details, type of nose flap and dimensions reported, and the weight and age of the calves studied.

Author(s)	Year	Title	Journal publication details	Type of nose flap	Length	Width	Septum gap	Days held in place	Calf age	Calf weight
Alvez, P., G. Quintans, M. J. Hötzel, and R. Ungerfeld.	2016	Two-step weaning in beef calves: permanence of nose flaps for 7 or 21 days does not influence the behaviour response	Anim. Prod. Sci. 56:866-870. doi:10.1071/AN14643	not reported	not reported	not reported	not reported	7 or 21 d	182.8 ± 1.2 d	162.5 ± 1.5 kg
Burke, N. C., G. Scaglia, H. T. Boland, and W. S. Swecker Jr.	2009	Influence of two-stage weaning with subsequent transport on body weight, plasma lipid peroxidation, plasma selenium, and on leukocyte glutathione peroxidase and glutathione reductase activity in beef calves	Vet. Immunol. Immunopathol. 127:365-370. doi:10.1016/j.vetimm.2008.11.017	Calf Weaner® C18349 N, Nasco, Fort Atkinson, WI	not reported	not reported	not reported	7 d	221 ± 19.7 d	243 ± 20.8 kg
de la Cruz-Cruz, L. A., H. Bonilla-Jaime, H. Orozco-Gregorio, J. M. Vargas-Romero, A. M. Tarazona-Morales, M. M.	2021	Effect of three weaning methods on behavioural, cortisol and weight changes in buffalo calves.	Anim. Prod. Sci. 61:780-789. doi:10.1071/AN20325.45	flexible polypropylene nose-flap devices	~13cm	9.5 cm	not reported	7 d	7-8 mo	247.05 ± 33.23 kg

Estévez-Cabrera,
and P. Roldán-
Santiago

de la Cruz-Cruz, L. A., H. Orozco-Gregorio, J. M. Vargas-Romero, S. Hernández-Arteaga, J. A. Sánchez-Salcedo, M. González-Hernández, G. Ballesteros-Rode, P. Roldán-Santiago, and H. Bonilla-Jaime.	2020	Physiological responses in weaned water buffalo calves with different separation strategies	. Livest. Sci. 23:1871-1413. doi:10.1016/j.livsci.2019.103892	flexible polypropylene nose-flaps devices COPAG®	13cm	9.5 cm	not reported	7 d	7-8 mo	229.05 ± 54 kg
Enríquez, D. H., R. Ungerfeld, G. Quintans, A. L. Guidoni, and M. J. Hötzel.	2010	The effects of alternative weaning methods on behaviour in beef calves	Livest. Sci. 128:20-27. doi:10.1016/j.livsci.2009.10.007	El Destete, Buenos Aires, Argentina;	12.5 cm	12.5 cm	not reported	17 d	180.7 ± 1.3 d	not reported
Freeman, S., M. Poore, C. Pickworth, and M. Alley.	2021	Influence of weaning strategy on behavior, humoral indicators of stress, growth, and carcass characteristics.	Transl. Anim. Sci. 5:1-16. doi:10.1093/tas/txaa23	not reported-resemble s Quiet Wean, JDA Livestock Innovations,	not reported	not reported	not reported	7 d	237 ± 3 d	254 ± 6.7 kg

Saskatoon,
Canada

Haley, D. B., D. W. Bailey, and J. M. Stookey.	2005	The effects of weaning beef calves in two stages on their behavior and growth rate	J. Anim. Sci. 83: 2205-2214. doi:10.2527/2005.8392205x	Villa Nueva S.A., Villa Maria-Cordoba, Argentina	12.0 cm	7.5 cm	not reported	3, 5 or 14 d	Trial 1: 187 ± 13 d & Trial 2: 189 ± 10 d & Trial 3: 181 ± 14 d	not reported
Hötzel, M. J., G. Quintans, and R. Ungerfeld.	2012	Behaviour response to two-step weaning is diminished in beef calves previously submitted to temporary weaning with nose flaps	Livest. Sci. 149:88-95. doi:10.1016/j.livsci.2012.06.029	El Destete, Argentina; see picture in Enriquez et al., 2010)	12.5 cm	12.5 cm	not reported	14 d	189 d	not reported
Lambertz, C., P. R. Bowen, G. Erhardt, and M. Gauly.	2015	Effects of weaning beef cattle in two stages or by abrupt separation on nasal abrasions, behaviour, and weight gain	Anim. Prod. Sci. 55:786-792. doi:10.1071/AN14097	Schipper s 0707085, Kerken, Germany (Plastic) and Schipper s 0703091, Kerken, Germany	~12 cm	~8 cm	not reported	7 d	222 ± 11 d	264 ± 40 kg

(Aluminum)

Lippolis, K. D., J. K. Ahola, C. E. Mayo, M. C. Fischer, and R. J. Callan.	2016	Effects of two-stage weaning with nose flap devices applied to calves on cow body condition, calf performance, and calf humoral immune response	J. Anim. Sci. 94:816-823. doi:10.2527/jas.2015-9624	QuietWean NF (JDA Livestock Innovations Ltd., Saskatchewan, Canada)	not reported	not reported	not reported	21 d	161 ± 22.7 d	179.4 ± 3.92 kg
Liu, P., S. Liu, A. Degen, Q. Qiu, Q. Dong, X. Jing, J. Zhang, Q. Yan, W. Zheng, and L. Ding	2018	Effect of weaning strategy on performance, behaviour and blood parameters of yak calves (<i>Poephagus grunniens</i>)	Rangel. J. 40:263-270. doi:10.1071/RJ17112.	not reported	not reported	not reported	not reported	15 d	94.3 ± 2.4 d	not reported
Loberg, J. M., C. E. Hernandez, T. Thierfelder, M. B. Jensen, C. Berg, and L. Lidfors.	2008	Weaning and separation in two steps—A way to decrease stress in dairy calves suckled by foster cows.	Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci. 111:222-234. doi:10.1016/j.applanim.2007.06.011	QuietWean nose-flap, JDA Livestock Innovations, Saskatoon, Canada	not reported	not reported	not reported	14 d	10 wk	not reported

Taylor, J. D., J. N. Gilliam, G. Mourer, and C. Stansberry.	2020	Comparison of effects of four weaning methods on health and performance of beef calves	Animal. 14:161-170. doi:10.1017/S1751731119001228	Orange plastic calf weaner, Syrvet, Inc. Lexington, KY, USA	not reported	not reported	not reported	6 d	241 d (range of 182 to 287) & 258 d (range of 210 to 292)	249 kg (range of 166 to 338) & 278 kg (range of 189 to 343)
Ungerfeld, R., G. Quintans, and M. J. Hötzel.	2016	Minimizing cows' stress when calves were early weaned using the two-step method with nose flaps	Animal. 10:1871–1876. doi:10.1017/S1751731116000793	El Destete, Buenos Aires, Argentina; see picture in Enríquez et al., 2010	12.5 cm	12.5 cm	not reported	5 d	not reported	not reported
Valente, T. S., L. R. B. Ruiz, F. Macitelli, and M. J. R. P. da Costa.	2022	Nose-flap devices used for two-stage weaning produce wounds in the nostrils of beef calves: Case report	Animals. 12:1452. doi:10.3390/ANI12111452	WalMur®, Brazil	13.5 cm	10cm	not reported	5 d	236 ± 4 d	not reported
